

**Sustainable
Medicines
Packaging**

AWARDS

YewMaker

Design Award

showcases innovations that reduce waste and increase sustainability of packaging without compromising function.

Circularity Award

showcases services, processes, or products that bring circularity into the supply chain to reduce single use.

2022 COMPETITION

Design Award

FINALISTS

1. **Dual Chamber Blister** - Pantec AG/Pharmapan
2. **Eastalite Universal Device Shipping Tray** - Plastic Ingenuity
3. **EcoSecur Type 2 Glass Vials** - Stoelzle Glass Group
4. **Phill Box** - Parcel Health
5. **Protecting the Product and the Environment** - Essentra Packaging
6. **Qube Pro** - Jones Healthcare Group
7. **Sustainable Grassboard in Pharma Packaging** - Körber Pharma Packaging Materials AG

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Stoelzle Glass Group

EcoSecur Type 2 Glass Vials

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

TYPE 2 GLASS VIALS

Stoelzle Pharma reached another milestone by developing a new, safe and resource-efficient process for the inner surface treatment of type 2 glass vials. This innovative technique enables reliable and precise dosing tailored to each bottle size, from the smallest 6 ml vials to much bigger. With EcoSecur injection and infusion vials, Stoelzle Pharma has reinvented type 2 glass for parenteral and non-parenteral applications.

INNOVATIVE PROCESS – LIQUID TREATMENT

A new, innovative process enables reliable and precise dosing tailored to the size of the glass. In our process, fewer chemicals are used and there are no toxic substances. At the same time, we can guarantee the highest product quality and increased work safety through lower contamination during the production process as well as safe storage and handling of raw materials.

YOUR BENEFITS

MINIMISED ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

achieved through precise and optimal dosage of ammonium sulfate – as much as necessary, as little as possible.

PROCESS STABILITY

offers our highest product quality for smaller (starting with 6 ml) and bigger vials through automated, consistent and precise treatment solution dosing.

SUPERIOR GLASS QUALITY

increased product safety through automated process controls and 100% treatment detection.

MINIMISED ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

suitable for most acidic and neutral aqueous preparations.

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Jones Healthcare Group

Qube Pro

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Designed for Automation Using Leading-Edge Sustainable Materials

The Qube Pro reduces sealing time by 50% with seamless automation compatibility and industry-leading sustainable construction from renewable resources. Discover how the Qube Pro helps your pharmacy achieve its goals.

- 1 Print patient information directly on the package — no need to apply additional labels — or use existing labels from the Qube product line
- 2 High-impact visuals align the package on automated or semi-automated machine filling trays. Compatible with any Qube product line automation tray
- 3 New medically approved Bio-PET blister contains 33% plant-based PET with an eco-friendly, foil-free backing
- 4 Patients can easily access medications with a unique push-and-tear perforated seal
- 5 High-capacity blisters for more medications
- 6 Smaller overall size compared to the Qube means less storage space, lower shipping costs and less waste
- 7 Measures 9 1/2" (tall) x 5-15/16"(wide) x 7/8" (deep) when completely assembled
- 8 Large text depicts the time of day to take medication
- 9 Easy grid system for patients to locate the correct medication pass
- 10 Lot number and date printed directly on the blister for full traceability

Qube Pro Multi-Medication System

Inside When Sealed

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Pantec AG / Pharmapan

Dual Chamber Blister

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

The Dual Chamber Blister - Dosepan®

Sustainability

Waste management – The compact Dual Chamber Blister device saves materials due to its lean and compact concept compared to the classical vial/syringe solution and reduces therefore waste. As an effect it helps to lower Cogs.

Energy consumption – Production processes as well as lower weight in shipping reduces saves energy. The footprint of the production equipment can be reduced substantially, and less cleanroom space is the consequence.

Administration advantages – The simple and safe use of the device allows healthcare workers to administrate the vaccination, no need of highly qualified medical staff. This is a benefit especially in GAVI countries. If the drug is formulated to be heat stable, the cooling chain could be superseded.

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Essentra Packaging

Protecting the Product and the Environment

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

DIATER

Packaging Material change to board

The company: Diater is a biopharmaceutical company, specialized in allergic, diseases that offers physicians a wide range of diagnosis and treatment products to significantly improve the quality of life of patients with allergies.

THE PRODUCT

The packaging is meant to transport vials for allergic diagnosis to doctors. The former packaging was produced with rigid plastic colored in orange and weighted 67 gr.

Before

After

With the new cartonboard packaging development that Essentra Packaging is currently producing, Diater has eliminated
1.67 Tons of plastic every year, meaning
3.35 Tons less CO₂_{eq} emissions yearly*.

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Parcel Health

Phill Box

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

PROBLEM

Every year, over 8 billion plastic prescription bottles are used and thrown away in the United States, generating the equivalent of more than 500 Boeing 747 planes in weight in plastic waste. These orange pill bottles are a relic of the past and offer limited functionality to patients and pharmacies.

OUR SOLUTION: THE PHILL BOX®

Parcel Health believes in a future of sustainable medication packaging that serves the modern patient. [View the animated tutorial here.](#)

KEY FEATURES

- Curbside recyclable, backyard compostable
- 3-step lock: toddler-resistant and elderly-friendly
- 30% smaller carbon footprint than plastic pill bottles
- Water-resistant and light-proof
- Compatible with all pharmacy labels and the Phill Label™ system

HOW TO USE IN PHARMACIES

Dispensing medications in a Phill Box is easy and very similar to filling an orange plastic pill bottle. The transition for pharmacies is seamless.

Circularity Award

FINALISTS

1. **"Cut the waste" Service through Liveo Optima Scientific Package Design Program** - Liveo Research Inc
2. **Circularity Solutions for Thermoformed Plastics Along the Pharma Value Chain** - Plastic Ingenuity
3. **Circularity-as-a-Service for Medicine Plastics** - Automedi
4. **eZCooler** - Zuellig Pharma
5. **Sharpsmart Reusable Containers** - Sharpsmart Ltd
6. **Smart Reusable Packaging** - Monoceros and Emball'Iso

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Zuellig Pharma

eZCooler

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

eZCooler solution:

The eco-friendly way to ensure the integrity of temperature-sensitive products on the road

The eZCooler solution is a thermal insulation system that can be customised to provide temperatures of down to -40°C for products that must be stored at the required temperature to maintain their integrity.

Environmentally friendly, does not require external energy source

4 days

Maximum number of days that eZCooler can maintain a required temperature

200 times

Exceedingly high re-usability rate per year, resulting in reduced box consumption

5 years

Long usable shelf life of at least 5 years to reduce footprints

ZER

No temperature excursion within validated hours

Extensive capability of operating temperature ranges and box sizes

-20°C to -40°C

-15°C to -25°C

2°C to 8°C

15°C to 25°C

Able to hold maintain temperatures up to 96 hours

Smallest: 8 litres
Largest: 960 litres

1,900 EPS box

500 eZCooler

=

40% reduction in CO2 emissions

+

92% reduction in waste

Over a 5 year period...

eZCooler is tested to international quality standards for the handling of pharma products before and during deployment to ensure its performance in field operations.

Pre-operation

Operation qualification:

Lab test or warehouse challenge test

Performance qualification:

Field runs simulating actual conditions

During operation

Routine monitoring:

Sample check on performance by reviewing shipment temperature data

Periodic review:

Yearly effectiveness study by payload, routes and temperature excursion risk

Countries using eZCooler

6,200 in use

Large scale implementation across region

making healthcare more accessible

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Monoceros & Emball' Iso

Smart Reusable Packaging

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

THE FIRST SMART AND REUSABLE PACKAGING

30% of pharma is discarded due to logistic issues

SINGLE-USE IMPACT

70% of the CO₂eq of packaging come from its production

80% of the CO₂eq of data-logger comes from its production

Package ready for delivery of new medicine
Logger receives updated conditions to monitor

Package is full
Live monitoring of location and conditions starts

Package cleaned, checked and sold on local market / new user
Logger automatic switch to storage mode until next delivery

Package collected by Emball'iso for reuse
Automatic end of delivery detection, no human needed

Package secures temperature conditions during transport
Continuous real-time monitoring and alerts for proactive actions

Package reached destination with medicines in perfect conditions
Data already on the platform and report ready for compliance

-30%

of pharma saved for damaged

REUSABLE IMPACT

-91%

of CO₂eq saved with reusable packaging

-98%

of CO₂eq saved with smart reusable data-loggers

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Automedi

Circularity-as-a-Service for Medicine Plastics

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Turnkey Circular Economy

Automedi is a Circularity-as-a-Service supporting businesses to change the game with sustainable manufacturing and supply that turning plastic waste into products, at the point of need.

Subscription turnkey circular economies (B2B2C)
 Launched: August 2020
 Workforce: 8
 Circularity-as-a-Service

Automedi combines recycling with a decentralised & distributed 3D printing fleet to recycle harvested medicine plastics into products at the touch of a button. Choosing from a catalogue on each device and making items easy as ordering from a vending machine.

Our fleet can also be organised into virtual factories for greater scale. Commandeering machines across a country, can make millions of items from that waste available in minutes.

ECONOMIC VALUE GENERATED

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Sharpsmart Ltd

Sharpsmart Reusable Containers

2022

Nazneen Rahman

CEO YewMaker

YewMaker

The Sharpsmart reusable container is arguably the world's most environmentally responsible pharmaceutical waste management system

Making Healthcare Safer & Our Environment Greener

Reusable reduces environmental impact & cost

Reusable means, quite simply, that containers are reused and not disposed via high temperature incineration (HTI). For the user and the environment, the benefits are trifold - diversion of non-biodegradable plastic from HTI, eliminating manufacture and purchase of new containers, and the supply of collectors fully assembled, and free of harmful chemical residue.

With safety as our primary driver, Sharpsmart have invested millions of dollars in R&D to develop world-leading robotic cleaning technology that achieves the highest levels of bacterial load reduction. Our 10-stage decanting, washing and decontamination process eliminates microbial contamination and ensures that all collectors entering a sterile environment are rendered free from contamination.

Eliminating 1.7 million single-use containers

A recent study published in the British Medical Journal open compared the impact on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, plastic manufactured and cardboard used, of 40 acute NHS Trust hospitals converting from single-use containers to the Sharpsmart reusable container system.

In the 12 months following conversion to the reusable system, the combined results for the 40 Trust were:

- ✔ Global warming potential (GWP) reduction of 3,267.4 tonnes of CO₂e (-83.9%).
- ✔ Elimination of incineration of 900.8 tonnes of plastic.
- ✔ Elimination of disposal/recycling of 132.5 tonnes of cardboard.
- ✔ Elimination of manufacture of 1.7 million single-use sharps containers
- ✔ A 61.1% reduction in labour required for sharps container exchanges.

Over the last 12 months, our pharmaceutical reusable container system has*:

- ▶ Collected **163.3 tonnes** of pharmaceutical waste
- ▶ Eliminated **45.06 tonnes** of single-use plastic
- ▶ Eliminated the manufacture and subsequent incineration of **46,938** disposable containers

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Plastic Ingenuity

Circularity Solutions for Thermoformed
Plastics Along the Pharma Value Chain

2022

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Forming a Better Future

Plastic Ingenuity is highly focused on making thermoformed plastic packaging more circular. Through innovation, education, and investment, we partner with our customers and the packaging value chain to reach sustainability & circularity goals by offering a range of services:

- Sustainable Packaging Assessment
- Life Cycle Analysis
- Recyclability Consulting
- Take-Back Programs
- Sustainability VOC
- PI Circular Newsletter
- PI Annual Circularity Report
- Good Information Video Series

CIRCULARITY AWARD

Vertically Integrated Take-Back Program

Case Study: Circularity of Autoinjector Packaging

18 autoinjectors per handling tray;
>103 MM autoinjectors per year (2021)

Circularity Solution:
 On-site grinding and recycling of trays
 from drug filling site

Estimated Annual Impact:
\$2.5 Million+ of cost savings
~5 Million lbs of virgin HIPS avoided

Scenario 3: Regional Recycling
 Send used parts to Material Reclamation Facilities with closer proximity to laboratories (end users) while incorporating as much post-consumer recycled PET into new parts

Result: Of the three proposed scenarios, #3 results in the lowest GHG emissions due to eliminating transportation

2023 COMPETITION

Design Award

FINALISTS

- **New IDC®** - Airnov Healthcare Packaging
- **AmSky™** - Amcor
- **Making Electricity with Paper & Enzymes** - BeFC
- **IGB Tamper Evident Folding Box** - Industrie Grafiche Bressan
- **PulPac + PA Consulting** - PulPac Dry Molded Fiber (DMF) Blister
- **PharmaGuard** - SÜDPACK Medica

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Amcor

AmSky™

2023

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Amcor HealthCare™ AmSky™ Blister System

VINYL & ALUMINUM FREE

RECYCLE-READY

LOWER CARBON FOOTPRINT

AmSky™ Blister System is a market-disrupting, recycle-ready, blister packaging system. It eliminates PVC and aluminum foil to provide a carbon footprint-optimized packaging alternative for pharmaceuticals and nutraceuticals.

Recycle ready, mono-material solution

AmSky™ is an industry-first recycle-ready blister package with thermoformed and lidding both made from HDPE.

Deliver on your **SUSTAINABILITY COMMITMENTS** without sacrificing performance.

76% reduction

in carbon footprint over PVC/foil blister packs.

Simplified supply chains

due to sourcing from a single supplier and global manufacturing sites.

77% reduction

in non-renewable energy demand for production compared to PVC/foil blister packs.

Combines senior friendliness and child resistance

in a single lidding with a push-through opening.

Provides an enhanced moisture barrier

to deliver shelf life same as 120gsm PVDc-coated PVC + foil lid.

Compatible with existing machinery

providing a turnkey solution for existing blister equipment.

Your customers want recyclability, and AmSky™ provides the industry's only mono-material solution for whole package recycling.

Benefits of working with Amcor

- Easier qualification – compliance with all applicable regulatory requirements
- Pharmaceutical packaging expertise – a world leader in high-barrier blister packaging solutions
- Reliable sourcing – multiple North American and European manufacturing sites for business continuity
- Quality assurance – ISO 13485 certified quality systems and rigorous focus on defect-free delivery

Discover Amcor's breakthroughs in sustainable packaging.
Visit www.amcor.com Contact us healthcare@amcor.com

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

PulPac + PA Consulting

PulPac Dry Molded Fiber (DMF) Blister

2023

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Creating a worlds' first pulp-based DMF tablet blister pack for RX and CX, using a unique dry production process that can be a like-for-like, scalable alternative to PVC.

DMF is the first industrial method that can convert renewable plant fibers into packaging, price competitive to replace single-use plastics at scale.

PULPAC DRY MOLDED FIBER (DMF) BLISTER

Why DMF For Blister Packs Excites Us:

Tablet blister packs as a sector is growing at Market Size

6.4%

CAGR and will reach **US\$22.9BN** by 2030

100,000t

Of plastic used in medication packaging per year

20%

The USA currently only has of its RX medication in blister packaging

Medicines packet recycling scheme scaled back following 'high uptake' and lack of infrastructure

Switching bottles to blister packs increased adherence

from **61%** to **97%**

Key Benefits of Using DMF:

80%

Lower CO₂ emissions compared to plastics & wet molding

Low

To almost no water use during dry production process

£

Cost parity to plastic costs at scale

Barrier

Suitability for low / mid / high needs

High

Surface finish achievable

Recyclable

In the paper waste stream

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

BeFC

Making Electricity with Papers & Enzymes

2023

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

BeFC : the sustainable energy solution for low power electronics.

About us

BeFC makes electricity from papers and enzymes. Our company offers an eco-friendly and sustainable energy solution for low-power electronics. We have developed a series of breakthrough innovations that allow the use of enzymes with carbon paper electrodes to generate useful amounts of energy through biocatalysis. A result of decades of pioneering research into the bioenzymatic processes and properties of paper materials, the intellectual property is protected by a 6-patent portfolio. BeFC is located in the heart of the Alps, Grenoble, with both R&D and prototyping facilities located just 100 m apart. Since our creation in 2020, BeFC has raised 5 M€ of investment, and is now developing the next generation of connected devices with our forward-thinking partners for multiple market sectors including IoT, logistics, medical, agriculture, and smart packaging.

Opportunity

There is a growing trend towards wearable and single-use/single-patient medical devices, connected packaging and IoT sensor solutions. Typically, these devices are powered by coin or button cell batteries. The problem: an average of 97% of miniature batteries typically end up in landfill or are incinerated. For many applications the battery presents additional cost and complexity to the collection, recycling, and disposal. BeFC has a strong commitment to sustainability, with the goal of replacing conventional batteries in disposable electronic devices with our paper-based biofuel cells, as well as providing new opportunities for innovation in emerging markets

Customer Benefits & Possible Applications

- Reduced costs of recycling / disposal
- Environmentally friendly & non-toxic
- Biosourced materials
- Ultra-thin & flexible
- Lightweight
- Metal-free
- Plastic-free
- Sustainable fuels
- Safe (no risk of auto-combustion)
- Form factor adjustable to application

info@befc.fr

Technology

Our solution is a biofuel cell that uses enzymes to convert sugar and oxygen into electricity. Our products are both metal-free and plastic-free. Being paper-based results in thin and flexible devices that are particularly suited for wearable sensors. The device can be activated using either a patented integrated liquid reservoir, or a tiny volume of biological or environmental liquid (e.g., tap water, urine, sweat). Once activated, energy is produced within a few seconds. Our paper fuel cells are capable of producing up to a few milliwatts per square centimeter, enough power for most modern sensors and low-power wireless transmitters for periods of minutes to months, depending on the mode of operation. BeFC also develops custom digital platforms optimised to our technology, allowing us to provide a complete electronic solution for our customers.

Together, power the future with nature.®

Circularity Award

FINALISTS

- **PulPac + PA Consulting** - PulPac Dry Molded Fiber (DMF) Blister
- **Sustainable Mineral Antimicrobial Technology** - Pylote SAS
- **PharmaGuard** - SÜDPACK Medica
- **SymbioTex Ltd** - Seaweed-based Home Compostable Medical Device

Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

SymbioTex Ltd

Seaweed-based Home Compostable Medical Devices

2023

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Since 2011, **73 million inhalers** have been distributed in the UK and only **1.3% have ever been recycled**. Even then inhalers still utilise non-renewable materials and after 4 recycling cycles- have to be landfilled.

We aim to put an **end to the landfilling of millions of tonnes** of medical devices by creating a plug and play solution to fossil fuels. We will licence our technology to current medical device manufacturers –our material is **processable on the same machinery** that is currently used but at lower temperatures- allowing plastic **companies to seamlessly transition to our material!**

Our technology also aims to displace bioplastics which are not truly sustainable, like those which compete with land used for crops, those that are only industrially compostable, or those that produce harmful by-products. Unlike most bioplastic companies -**we use 100% of the (seaweed) biomass**. We aim to produce class 1 medical devices such as inhalers, covid-19 tests, pregnancy tests and other diagnostic test kits. The **inhaler market alone is worth £34.6 billion a year** and annually growing at a rate of 25.1%.

The medical industry has so far been left untouched when it comes to sustainable materials! No one is aiming to produce **biobased home compostable class 1 medical devices** as we are! We already have **interest from several NHS Trusts** who we aim to undertake focus groups by the end of this year! We have the **support of Medilink, AHSN, and Ocean Healthcare**; we are working with medical device design companies (Haughton Design and Amies Innovation)- who have customers already asking them for these solutions.

Previous to our patent submission in March 2023 we undertook a preliminary patent search in addition to freedom to operate evaluation. Our **submitted formulation patent** covers any application of our material with the use of any seaweed (brown, red or green).

Our solution will **reduce the costs and environmental impacts** associated with the disposal of the medical plastic waste and reduce the high taxations that these organisations will be subjected to. We aim for our technology to have a large impact - **we tackle 9 out of 17 UN SDGs!**

Licensing our technology to existing manufactures will allow class 1 medical devices to become home compostable and prevent millions of tonnes of plastic going to landfill.

Winner's Certificate

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PulPac + PA Consulting

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Recyclable

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Winner's Certificate

THIS AWARD IS PRESENTED TO

Pylote SAUS

Sustainable Mineral Antimicrobial Technology

2023

Nazneen Rahman
CEO YewMaker

Entry for sustainable medicines packaging awards 2023

PYLOTE's SUSTAINABLE MINERAL ANTIMICROBIAL TECHNOLOGY

- 100% mineral, biocompatible & patented technology from production to application, manufactured in France using in-house green chemistry process.
- An innovation and a method unique in the world: *La Pyrolyse Pulvérisée®* with a responsible one step manufacturing process 100% mineral, clean & green chemistry.
- To contribute to a better world through a natural approach in order to better protect populations and environments, by being able to respond to proven risks of microbial contamination linked to products or living areas.
- To provide consumers or patients with greener, cleaner and safer solutions for which there is a demonstrated need for antimicrobial protection, with three complementary objectives:
 1. The maintenance of microbiological hygiene.
 2. Safeguarding the product throughout its life cycle.
 3. Reduction of the ecological footprint.
- Fully compliant, stable and biocompatible while certified non-irritant and non-cytotoxic Ecocert technology.
- Immediate, stable and permanent action of the technology with efficiency tested in independent laboratory on SARS CoV-2 and its Delta variant (>96% in 1h) and on bacteria (>99,999% in 24h + Tests in real conditions in situ with important circulation of people).

Activated Rispharm*

An antimicrobial ophthalmic multidose dropper to help reduce eye microbial infections for consumers

An antimicrobial ophthalmic multidose dropper to help reduce eye microbial infections for consumers

- Hygienic applications for every use with a multidose dropper.
- Proven and certified effective against conjunctivitis virus, *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria.
- Breakthrough sustainable innovation.
- Self-decontamination of tip and cap.
- Identical patient treatment method.
- Same packaging design and use of existing manufacturing/filling lines.
- 16 times less plastic waste compared to monodose option.

**Developed by Pylote in partnership with BERRY GLOBAL*

CONGRATULATIONS!

